

DSL Usability Evaluation

In dieser Umfrage sind 31 Fragen enthalten.

Preparations and Domain Introduction.

The Otk-DL solves the problem where we want to use OpenTelemetry as a monitoring agent and send the information to the Kieker endpoint.

The problem is that OpenTelemetry provides flexible data structures, like Spans, where the user can add arbitrary attributes to the Span object. Kieker, on the other hand, relies on the fixed data structures and fixed order of attributes that are sent over TCP streams. This means that it is not feasible to provide a universal OpenTElemetry supporter for Kieker, because for each Kieker record you would need your own implementation.

Another problem is that users of OpenTelemetry who want to use KiekerAnalysis might have problems with the limited choice of predefined monitoring records that Kieker understands. To address this issue, our DSL provides means to specify custom monitoring records and mappings of how certain span parameters should correspond to Kieker monitoring record attributes.

We also allow to generate code for Kieker Collector that is capable of understanding these custom records.

In this task section, we will make sure that you have all the necessary dependencies and tools installed in order to use our ticket generator and participate in this survey.

Before we start, let's familiarize ourselves with the tools. If you participate on this surveying your computer, please clone [following git repository](#) to your machine.

The survey will require you to do some java and python coding. It is important to ensure that your setup on machine fullfils the technical requirements. If you wish to setup everything locally on your machine, please, clone [this git repository](#) and do all the steps bellow.

If you do this survey on the machine of the survey supervisor, you can skip this section entirely.

Bitte wählen Sie eine der folgenden Antworten:

Bitte wählen Sie nur eine der folgenden Antworten aus:

Step 1: Make sure that you have at least version 21 of Java installed.

Bitte wählen Sie eine der folgenden Antworten:

Bitte wählen Sie nur eine der folgenden Antworten aus:

Keine Antwort

Step 2: Make sure you have Python 12 installed on your machine.

Bitte wählen Sie eine der folgenden Antworten:

Bitte wählen Sie nur eine der folgenden Antworten aus:

No Answer

Step 3: Make sure you have the pip package manager installed.

Bitte wählen Sie eine der folgenden Antworten:

Bitte wählen Sie nur eine der folgenden Antworten aus:

No Answer

Step 4: Create a python virtual environment, by running:

`python -m venv venv`

Activate the environment

`source venv/bin/activate` if using Linux/macOs

`venv\Scripts\activate` if using Windows

Bitte geben Sie Ihre Antwort hier ein:

Step 5: Inside of the git repo, you will find a requirements.txt.

Run ``pip install -r requirements.txt`` to install all necessary Python dependencies.

Bitte geben Sie Ihre Antwort hier ein:

Step 6: Browse to the Survey Setup folder.

You will find two directories: *example-app* and *collector*. You will also find a *config.txt* file.

Please open the *config.txt* file.

Search for *kieker.monitoring.writer.filesystem.FileWriter.customStoragePath=*.

This option defines where the monitoring logs should be stored. Please enter the absolute path where the logs should be stored.

You can also leave the entry provided by default by us, which is recommended, if you do the survey on the machine of the survey supervisor.

Bitte geben Sie Ihre Antwort hier ein:

Step 7: Open the *collector* folder. Run *mvn clean package*.

Bitte geben Sie Ihre Antwort hier ein:

Step 8: Go to the target folder. You will find two jars there.

Run `java -jar Collector-0.0.1-SNAPSHOT-jar-with-dependencies.jar -c path/to/config.txt`.

The collector should start. If there are no exceptions, you can assume that everything is running as planned.

Bitte geben Sie Ihre Antwort hier ein:

Step 9: Now go back to the `survey-setup` folder. From there, change to the `example-app` folder.

You might need to reactivate the python environment.

Run the `example.py` Python script.

Go to the directory you specified as the output for your collector.

There you will see log.files generated by the collector. You should see entries in each of them. If you can confirm this, the setup is complete and you can proceed with the survey.

Bitte geben Sie Ihre Antwort hier ein:

Step 10: Go back to the root of the repository. Locate demo folder and open it.

Bitte geben Sie Ihre Antwort hier ein:

Step 11: You will find otkt.jar, example.otkt and the templates directory.

**Run `java -jar otkt.jar absolute/path/to/example.otkt
absolute/path/to/output/destination`**

The generator will create a collector and python directories in the output directory that you provided as second argument.

You can delete them now that you have learned how to use the generator.

Last but not least, we also provide shell scripts, that will automate the starting of the collector and running of the Otkt-New.jar. We recommend you to utilize this scripts, but if you wish you can do everything also manually.

The automated scripts lie in `coding_task/manual` and `coding_task/DSL` directories. To run them, simply type `./testandrund.sh` into the terminal.

Bitte geben Sie Ihre Antwort hier ein:

Demographics and Experience

In this section, we aim to learn more about your background and experience to better understand your feedback on the DSL. Please answer the questions honestly. Your responses will only be used for evaluation purposes and will remain anonymous. Thank you for your participation!

1. What is your primary role?

Wählen Sie alle zutreffenden Optionen

Bitte wählen Sie alle zutreffenden Antworten aus:

- Kieker Developer
- Student
- Researcher
- Other

1. How would you rate your experience level with Kieker?

Bitte wählen Sie eine der folgenden Antworten:

Bitte wählen Sie nur eine der folgenden Antworten aus:

- None
- Beginner
- Intermediate
- Expert

1. How would you rate your experience level with OpenTelemetry?

Bitte wählen Sie eine der folgenden Antworten:

Bitte wählen Sie nur eine der folgenden Antworten aus:

- None
- Beginner
- Intermediate
- Expert

How would you rate your experience level with Python programming language?

Bitte wählen Sie eine der folgenden Antworten:

Bitte wählen Sie nur eine der folgenden Antworten aus:

- None
- Beginner
- Intermediate
- Expert

How would you rate your experience level with Java programming language?

Bitte wählen Sie eine der folgenden Antworten:

Bitte wählen Sie nur eine der folgenden Antworten aus:

- None
- Beginner
- Intermediate
- Expert

Section 2: DSL Interpretation Task

You will be shown several DSL code excerpts. For each excerpt, please describe in your own words what you think the code is trying to express or achieve.

What does this DSL code try to express?

```
3 Span: Foo {
4   trace: trace
5   parentTrace: parentspan
6   spanId: spanId
7   startT: startT
8   endT: endT
9
10  attributes:type string message
11  type bool is_off
12  type int int_num
13  type long long_num
14  type int branch_id
15  type int branching_outcome
16 }
17
18 Reuse: BranchingRecord
19 Mapping: Foo ->BranchingRecord{
20   Foo.startT to BranchingRecord.timestamp
21   Foo.branch_id to BranchingRecord.branchID
22   Foo.branching_outcome to BranchingRecord.branchingOutcome
23 }
24
25 collector:{
26   1234
27   "localhost"
28 }
29
```

Bitte geben Sie Ihre Antwort hier ein:

What does this DSL code express?

```
3 Span: Foo {
4   trace: trace
5   parentTrace: parentspan
6   spanId: spanId
7   startT: startT
8   endT: endT
9
10  attributes:type string message
11  type bool is_off
12  type int int_num
13  type long long_num
14  type int branch_id
15  type int branching_outcome
16 }
17
18
19 new: CustomRecord2 normal
20   long trace
21   long spanId
22   string message
23   bool flag
24 }
25
26 Mapping: Foo -> CustomRecord2{
27   Foo.message to CustomRecord2.message
28   Foo.is_off to CustomRecord2.flag
29   Foo.trace to CustomRecord2.trace
30   Foo.spanId to CustomRecord2.spanId
31 }
```

Bitte geben Sie Ihre Antwort hier ein:

What is the difference between those mapping syntaxes? Hint: BranchingRecord is a default record provided by Kieker out of Box.

```
25 Mapping: Foo ->BranchingRecord{
26     Foo.endTime to BranchingRecord.timestamp
27     Foo.branch_id to BranchingRecord.branchID
28     Foo.branching_outcome to BranchingRecord.branchingOutcome
29 }
30 default mapping Foo -> BranchingRecord
31
```

Bitte geben Sie Ihre Antwort hier ein:

In your opinion, what could keywords normal and flow indicate?

```
3 new: CustomRecord normal {
9     int numeric
9     string text
1    bool flag
2 }
3
4 new: CustomRecord2 flow {
5     int bar|
5 }
```

Bitte geben Sie Ihre Antwort hier ein:

In the following span, the last two custom attributes seem to exhibit additional properties. What could these be?

```
Span: Foo {  
  trace: trace  
  parentTrace: parentspan  
  spanId: spanId  
  startT: startT  
  endT: endT  
  
  attributes: type string message  
  type bool is_off  
  type int int_num  
  type long long_num  
  type int branch_id inc by 1 dependsOn: global  
  type int branching_outcome inc by 1 dependsOn: parent  
}
```

Bitte geben Sie Ihre Antwort hier ein:

Otk Demo

The following tasks will familiarize you with the the usage of Otk generator and Otk syntax and prepare you to the next tasks.

Navigate to `"/coding_task/"`.

Here you will find two directories.

`/manual` contains files necessary for the task where you will be prompted to manually create a Kieker Monitoring Record class and an OpenTelemetry exporter. You need to edit the `CustomRecord.java` in the `"/coding_task/manual/collector/src/java/main/CustomRecords"` directory. You will also need to manually edit `"/coding_task/manual/python-templates/kiekerexporter.py"`.

In `"/coding_task/DSL/"` you will find a `"survey.otkt"` file that you need to populate with a DSL code.

Bitte geben Sie Ihre Antwort hier ein:

Go to the demo directory of the git repo you cloned at the beginning and read the READMEs to familiarize yourself with the syntax of the Otkit DSL.

Bitte geben Sie Ihre Antwort hier ein:

Section 3: Productivity Evaluation

In this section, you will complete two tasks:

1. **Manual Implementation:** You will create a custom OpenTelemetry (OTel) exporter in Python and a corresponding Kieker monitoring record in Java manually.
2. **DSL-Based Implementation:** You will use our DSL to generate the same files.

The goal is to compare the manual process with the DSL-assisted process in terms of ease, efficiency, and accuracy. Please follow the provided instructions carefully for each task.

Create necessary files manually to be able to send the following Kieker MonitoringRecord using OpenTelemetry as a monitoring agent:

Create Java class CustomRecord: with the following parameters: long timestamp, String helloWorld, int myNum, long spanId.

Also, edit kiekerexporter.py such that span values are correctly serialized and sent in the correct order.

These parameters should be mapped as follows to the following span attributes in the Python Exporter:

```
start_time = timestamp  
message = helloWorld  
int_num = myNum  
span_id= spanId
```

Consult the tutorials, and example files or ask the survey supervisor if you have questions about Kieker or the OTel API.

If you think you are ready, try to run testandrun.sh script to check if you produced runnable results.

If your code does not compile or produce expected output (Kieker Monitoring log from collector), try to fix errors, and try again.

How much time did it take to create necessary files manually?

Bitte geben Sie Ihre Antwort hier ein:

Create the same files using our DSL to send the following Kieker MonitoringRecord to Custom Kieker Collector using OpenTelemetry as the monitoring agent. The DSL code should be stored in survey.otkt file.

At the end the run testandrun.sh again to verify the correctness of the generated file. Like in previous equstions, if you code does not compile or generate expected output in form of Kieker Monitoring logs in collector, fix the errors, and try again. Consult the survey supervisor if you have any technical questions or questions about how to run certain tools that are not clear.

How much time did it take to create the necessary files using DSL?

Bitte geben Sie Ihre Antwort hier ein:

How would you rate the ease of completing of each task? (1 = Very Difficult, 10 = Very Easy)

Bitte geben Sie Ihre Antwort(en) hier ein:

Manually

DSL

What challenges did you face during both of the tasks?

Bitte geben Sie Ihre Antwort hier ein:

Section 4: DSL Usability Feedback

How easy was it to understand the DSL syntax? (1 = Very Difficult, 10 = Very Easy)

In dieses Feld dürfen nur Zahlen eingegeben werden.

Bitte geben Sie Ihre Antwort hier ein:

How intuitive was the process of using the DSL? (1 = Very Unintuitive, 10 = Very Intuitive)

In dieses Feld dürfen nur Zahlen eingegeben werden.

Bitte geben Sie Ihre Antwort hier ein:

Here you have the possibility to give any feedback or opinion, if the previous questions did not cover the topic.

Bitte geben Sie Ihre Antwort hier ein:

Senden Sie Ihre Umfrage ein.

Vielen Dank für die Beantwortung des Fragebogens.